

Origin of the step structure of molecular exchange-correlation potentials

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The exact exchange-correlation potential of a stretched heteronuclear diatomic molecule exhibits a localized upshift in the region around the more electronegative atom; by this device the Kohn–Sham scheme ensures that the molecule dissociates into neutral atoms. Baerends and co-workers showed earlier that the upshift originates in the response part of the exchange-correlation potential. We describe a reliable numerical method for constructing the response potential of a given many-electron system and report accurate plots of this quantity. We also demonstrate that the step feature itself can be obtained directly from the interacting wavefunction of the system by computing the so-called average local electron energy. These findings illustrate in previously unavailable detail the mechanism of the formation of the upshift and the role played by static correlation in this process.

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate description of bond-breaking processes remains one of the principal challenges for approximate density-functional methods.¹ To develop density-functional approximations that correctly describe bond-breaking, it is essential to understand how the *exact* Kohn–Sham density-functional theory (DFT) arrives at the right answers when applied to stretched molecules. The central equation of the Kohn–Sham scheme is²

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + v(\mathbf{r}) + v_{\text{H}}(\mathbf{r}) + v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}) \right] \phi_i(\mathbf{x}) = \epsilon_i \phi_i(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{r}\sigma$ is a collective (spatial and spin) electron coordinate, $\phi_i(\mathbf{x})$ are the Kohn–Sham spin-orbitals, ϵ_i are the Kohn–Sham orbital energies, $v(\mathbf{r})$ is the external potential of the system, $v_{\text{H}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the Coulomb potential of the electron density, and $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the effective exchange-correlation potential whose role is to ensure that the electron density of the Kohn–Sham noninteracting system is the same as the true electron density.

Consider the dissociation of a heteronuclear diatomic molecule AB into neutral atoms A and B. The isolated atoms A and B have different external potentials and hence different Kohn–Sham highest-occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) energies, $\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{A}}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{B}}$. In the exact Kohn–Sham scheme, these energies are such that $\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{A}} = -I_{\text{A}}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{B}} = -I_{\text{B}}$, where I_{A} and I_{B} are the first ionization energies of A and B, respectively.^{3–6}

Suppose for the sake of definiteness that $I_{\text{A}} < I_{\text{B}}$. Then for the isolated atoms $\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{A}} > \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{B}}$. On the other hand, if A and B are viewed as constituent parts of a dissociated AB molecule, then the variational principle for the total energy implies⁶ that the HOMO levels of A and B must be equal, $\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{A}} = \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{B}}$. In approximate DFT, the equalization in the dissociated molecule is attained by transferring a fractional electron charge from A to B, which is physically incorrect. In the exact DFT, the equilibration is accomplished via the elevation of a region of $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ around nucleus B by a constant equal to^{6,7}

$$\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{A}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{B}} = I_{\text{B}} - I_{\text{A}}. \quad (2)$$

In other words, the exchange-correlation potential well of the more electronegative atom B in the separated AB system becomes upshifted by $I_{\text{B}} - I_{\text{A}}$ relative to the well of atom A. This upshift creates a characteristic step structure of the exact $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$, also known as the “counterionic field”, which prevents the electron density from flowing toward the more electronegative atom. Moreover, when A and B are not bonded, the step is enhanced by a peak separating the potential wells of the two atoms.⁶ In commonly used density-functional approximations for $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$, these features are absent, which is why one often finds that atoms in stretched molecules carry fractional charges.⁸

The steps and barriers of molecular exchange-correlation potentials have been extensively studied both analytically and numerically by Baerends, Gritsenko, and co-workers^{9–13} and later by other groups.^{14–19} The approach of Baerends, Gritsenko and co-workers is based on an exact partitioning of $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ derived from first principles,^{20–23}

$$v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}) = v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r}) + v_{c,\text{kin}}(\mathbf{r}) + v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r}). \quad (3)$$

Here $v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the exchange-correlation hole potential of the interacting system, $v_{c,\text{kin}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the kinetic correlation potential (the difference of interacting and noninteracting kinetic energies per electron), and $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the “response potential”

$$v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r}) = v^{N-1}(\mathbf{r}) - v_s^{N-1}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (4)$$

where $v_s^{N-1}(\mathbf{r})$ is defined in terms of the system’s Kohn–Sham orbitals and orbital energies,²¹ and $v^{N-1}(\mathbf{r})$ is defined in terms of wavefunction quantities.^{21,23}

By examining the analytic properties of each component of $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$, Gritsenko and Baerends identified¹⁰ $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ as the term responsible for the localized upshift of the potential around the more electronegative atom in a molecule. They also illustrated their conclusions numerically using the following method:^{9–12} (i) obtain an accurate ground-state electron density from a high-quality correlated wave function; (ii) construct the corresponding $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ by fitting it to the density using an iterative local update procedure, which also gives

the Kohn–Sham orbitals and orbital energies associated with $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$; (iii) calculate $v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r})$ and $v_{c,\text{kin}}(\mathbf{r})$ from the wavefunction and the Kohn–Sham orbitals; (iv) finally, obtain the response term as the difference

$$v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r}) = v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}) - v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r}) - v_{c,\text{kin}}(\mathbf{r}). \quad (5)$$

This indirect path to $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ has to deal with various numerical and basis-set artifacts^{9,10,23,24} associated with fitting exchange-correlation potentials to target electron densities. These artifacts then show up in plots of the response potential as spurious or exaggerated wiggles, dips near the nuclei, and other distortions.^{9–12}

Recently, we derived^{25–27} a new analytic expression for the wavefunction component of $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ in terms of eigenfunctions of the generalized Fock operator for the interacting wavefunction of the system. This expression allows one to generate $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ without fitting $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ to a target density. In this work, we use our expression for $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ to compute and plot this quantity with previously unavailable accuracy and detail. Our results provide the clearest and most direct illustration to date that the localized upshifts of $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ are encoded in the wavefunction component of the response term.

II. METHODS

This section describes our method of calculating the exchange-correlation potential and its response term. We start by listing the required ingredients.

A. Ingredients

Consider the ground state of a system of N interacting electrons. Let $\Gamma(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2; \mathbf{x}'_1, \mathbf{x}'_2)$ be the two-electron reduced density matrix (2-RDM) for this system calculated by some *ab initio* method. From the 2-RDM one can extract the 1-RDM

$$\gamma^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}'_1) = \frac{2}{N-1} \int [\Gamma(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2; \mathbf{x}'_1, \mathbf{x}'_2)]_{\mathbf{x}_2=\mathbf{x}'_2} d\mathbf{x}_2, \quad (6)$$

the positive-definite form of the interacting kinetic energy density

$$\tau^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \nabla_{\mathbf{r}'} \sum_{\sigma\sigma'} \gamma^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \right]_{\mathbf{r}'=\mathbf{r}}, \quad (7)$$

the electron density

$$\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\sigma} \gamma^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}), \quad (8)$$

and the exchange-correlation hole potential

$$v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r}) = \int \frac{\rho_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_2)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_2|} d\mathbf{r}_2, \quad (9)$$

where $\rho_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_2)$ is the exchange-correlation hole defined by the equation²⁸

$$\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}) [\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}_2) + \rho_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_2)] = 2 \sum_{\sigma\sigma_2} \Gamma(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_2; \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_2). \quad (10)$$

Let us also consider the generalized Fock integral operator^{29–32} \hat{G} whose kernel is given by

$$G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \left[-\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 + v(\mathbf{r}) \right] \gamma^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') + 2 \int \frac{\Gamma(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_2; \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_2)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_2|} d\mathbf{x}_2. \quad (11)$$

This operator is Hermitian for variational methods and non-Hermitian otherwise.³² One can always symmetrize this operator as

$$\hat{F} = \frac{1}{2} (\hat{G} + \hat{G}^\dagger) \quad (12)$$

and then solve the Hermitian eigenvalue problem

$$\int F(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') f_j(\mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}' = \lambda_j f_j(\mathbf{x}). \quad (13)$$

The eigenfunctions $f_j(\mathbf{x})$ are orthonormal and span the same space as the one-electron basis functions used to generate the 2-RDM. The total number of the eigenfunctions $f_j(\mathbf{x})$ is therefore equal to the number of linearly independent one-electron basis functions.

In the Kohn–Sham description of the system, the ground-state electron density is given by

$$\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^N |\phi_i(\mathbf{x})|^2 \quad (14)$$

and the positive-definite form of the noninteracting kinetic energy density is

$$\tau^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^N |\nabla \phi_i(\mathbf{x})|^2. \quad (15)$$

By the construction of the Kohn–Sham scheme,

$$\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r}) = \rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}). \quad (16)$$

The kinetic correlation potential may then be written as^{25–27}

$$v_{c,\text{kin}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\tau^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})}{\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})} - \frac{\tau^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})}{\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})}, \quad (17)$$

where the superscripts in ρ^{WF} and ρ^{KS} are retained to indicate the origin of these densities.

B. Calculation of the response term

In Ref. 27 we showed that the response potential may be obtained as

$$v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r}) = \bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r}) - \bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (18)$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the Kohn–Sham average local electron energy (ALEE) given by

$$\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})} \sum_{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^N \epsilon_i |\phi_i(\mathbf{x})|^2, \quad (19)$$

and $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the wavefunction ALEE given by

$$\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})} \sum_{\sigma} \sum_j \lambda_j |f_j(\mathbf{x})|^2, \quad (20)$$

in which the summation is over all eigenfunctions of \hat{F} . These quantities are referred to as ALEEs because each of them may be written as the sum of a local kinetic energy per electron and an effective potential.³³

The quantities $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$ are formally related to the components of Eq. (4) by the formulas²⁷

$$v_s^{N-1}(\mathbf{r}) = -\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}) - I, \quad (21)$$

where I is the first vertical ionization energy of the interacting system, and

$$v_s^{N-1}(\mathbf{r}) = -\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r}) + \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}, \quad (22)$$

where ϵ_{HOMO} is the exact Kohn–Sham HOMO eigenvalue. These relations hold exactly for exact wavefunctions, when $\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}} = -I$.

The wavefunction part of the response term, $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$, can be constructed in several different ways:²⁷ (i) from the Dyson orbitals and ionization energies of the system,²³ (ii) as the sum of a local kinetic energy per electron and $v(\mathbf{r}) + v_{\text{H}}(\mathbf{r}) + v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r})$ ^{33,34} (which follows from the expression²¹ for $v^{N-1}(\mathbf{r})$ in terms of conditional probability amplitudes), and (iii) from the eigenfunctions and eigenvalues of the generalized Fock operator³³ by Eq. (20). Of these expressions, the first one is clearly impractical; the second requires at most the diagonal part of the 2-RDM but produces plots that are distorted by Gaussian basis-set artifacts (unphysical oscillations and divergences similar to those reported for the inverted Kohn–Sham equation^{35,36}); the third expression requires no more than the 2-RDM and is numerically robust. It is this last representation of $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ that we will employ here.

Thus, to construct $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ by our method we need to evaluate its two components, $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$ by Eq. (19) and $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ by Eq. (20). The component $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ involves only wavefunction quantities and can be directly computed from a 2-RDM. The component $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$, however, involves the Kohn–Sham orbitals and orbital energies of the system, which are determined by $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ and are initially

unknown (note that construction of v_{resp} by Eq. (5) also required Kohn–Sham orbitals for the term $v_{c,\text{kin}}$). We showed previously^{25,26} that these unknowns can be numerically extracted from the 2-RDM through iterative solution of a nonlinear equation relating $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$, $\phi_i(\mathbf{x})$, and ϵ_i to certain wavefunction-based quantities. This equation has the general form of Eq. (3) with special representations for the kinetic correlation and response terms. Explicitly,^{25–27}

$$v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}) = v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r}) + \frac{\tau^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})}{\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})} - \frac{\tau^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})}{\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})} + \bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r}) - \bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (23)$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ is given specifically by Eq. (20). In this work, we use the original version of this iterative technique as implemented by Ryabinkin, Kohut, and Staroverov (RKS).²⁵ (The technique described by Cuevas-Saavedra, Ayers, and Staroverov²⁶ differs from the RKS procedure in details of the calculation of $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$, but otherwise is equivalent.)

The RKS procedure involves the following steps. First, we run an *ab initio* calculation on the system of interest and compute the wavefunction ingredients $\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$, $\tau^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$, $v_{\text{XC}}^{\text{hole}}(\mathbf{r})$, and $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ of Eq. (20) from the resulting 2-RDM. Then we generate a reasonable initial guess for $\phi_i(\mathbf{x})$ and ϵ_i using any standard density-functional approximation, substitute this guess into Eq. (23), solve the Kohn–Sham eigenvalue problem (1) in the same one-electron basis that was used to generate the wavefunction quantities, and repeat the cycle until the potential $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ is converged. Our convergence criterion is that the Kohn–Sham density matrices from two consecutive iterations differ by less than 10^{-10} in the root-mean-square sense. Matrix elements of all ingredients of $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ are computed by standard numerical integration techniques used in density-functional methods. The potential $v_{\text{H}}(\mathbf{r})$ appearing in Eq. (1) is the Coulomb potential of the current Kohn–Sham density $\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$; the matrix elements of $v_{\text{H}}(\mathbf{r})$ are computed analytically in terms of integrals involving one-electron basis functions. Other details of the RKS method may be found in Refs. 25 and 26.

A special note should be made on the meaning of potentials obtained by the RKS method in finite basis sets. The exchange-correlation potential obtained by the RKS method for a given 2-RDM is the true $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ corresponding to $\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ only when all the ingredients of Eq. (23) are generated and handled in a complete basis set. In a finite basis set, the RKS method produces a well-defined, smooth, oscillation-free approximation to the basis-set-limit $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ at the level of that finite basis. The density $\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$ arising as a byproduct of the RKS method is not exactly equal to $\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ in a finite basis set, but it tends to $\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ in the basis-set limit.^{25,26} For wavefunctions computed in large Gaussian basis sets, exchange-correlation potentials obtained by the RKS method are visually indistinguishable from the corresponding exact potentials, and $\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$ is practically identical to $\rho^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$.^{25,26,37,38}

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We chose to revisit the LiH molecule ($R_e = 1.5949 \text{ \AA}$) whose exchange-correlation potentials were studied earlier by Gritsenko *et al.*^{9,10,22} Although the steps and barriers of the exact $v_{XC}(\mathbf{r})$ are qualitatively reproduced by the RKS method even for relatively crude correlated wavefunctions and modest basis sets,^{25,26} in this work we decided to aim for higher accuracy. To this end, we employed full configuration interaction (FCI) wavefunctions for LiH generated in the fully uncontracted version of Jensen's pc-2 basis set, referred to as u-pc-2: (10s,4p,1d) for Li and (6s,2p,1d) for H,^{39,40} with pure d functions. We uncontracted the basis set to make it sufficiently flexible in atomic core regions.²⁶

Figure 1 shows that, in agreement with previous studies,^{9,10,22} the step structure of the exact $v_{XC}(\mathbf{r})$ for a stretched LiH molecule ($R = 3R_e$) originates in the response term, and that the barrier separating the exchange-correlation potential wells for Li and H arises mostly from the kinetic-correlation contribution.

Let us now examine each of the two components of the response potential, $\bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\bar{\epsilon}^{WF}(\mathbf{r})$. One can show³³ that, for an exact wavefunction, both $\bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\bar{\epsilon}^{WF}(\mathbf{r})$ asymptotically approach the negative of the first vertical ionization energy of the system,

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r}) = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\epsilon}^{WF}(\mathbf{r}) = -I. \quad (24)$$

Moreover, for any one-electron system, both $\bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\bar{\epsilon}^{WF}(\mathbf{r})$ are constants everywhere.

For an approximate wavefunction, $\bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r})$ approaches ϵ_{HOMO} , whereas $\bar{\epsilon}^{WF}(\mathbf{r})$ approaches²⁶ the negative of the first vertical ionization energy computed by the extended Koopmans' theorem⁴¹⁻⁴⁸ (EKT), $-I^{\text{EKT}}$. The EKT ionization potentials computed from the FCI/u-pc-2 wave-

FIG. 1: Exchange-correlation potential and its components obtained for LiH from the FCI/u-pc-2 wavefunction. The exchange-correlation potential well of the H atom is elevated by $I_H - I_{\text{Li}}$ relative to the well of Li.

TABLE I: Ionization energies of the isolated Li and H atoms computed by the EKT from the FCI/u-pc-2 wavefunction and the corresponding exact values from Ref. 49.

Atom	I, E_h	
	EKT	Exact
H	0.4999	0.5000
Li	0.1979	0.1981

function are very good approximations to the exact I_H and I_{Li} values (Table I).

Because $I_{\text{Li}} < I_H$, the first ionization energy of the separated LiH is $I_{\text{LiH}} = I_{\text{Li}}$. Therefore, both the Kohn-Sham and wavefunction ALEEs in separated LiH must approach $-I_{\text{Li}}$ in every direction. That is precisely what $\bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r})$ does in the HOMO-dominated regions $\Omega_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{LiH}}$ of a stretched LiH molecule (Fig. 2),

$$\bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r} \in \Omega_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{LiH}}) = -I_{\text{Li}}. \quad (25)$$

The wavefunction ALEE behaves quite differently (Fig. 2): it agrees with $\bar{\epsilon}^{KS}(\mathbf{r})$ in the region dominated by the HOMO of the Li atom,

$$\bar{\epsilon}^{WF}(\mathbf{r} \in \Omega_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{Li}}) = -I_{\text{Li}}, \quad (26)$$

but dips to $-I_H$ in the region dominated by the HOMO of the H atom,

$$\bar{\epsilon}^{WF}(\mathbf{r} \in \Omega_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{H}}) = -I_H, \quad (27)$$

before returning to the $-I_{\text{Li}}$ asymptote (not shown). This occurs because the Li and H atoms in a stretched LiH molecule are almost isolated, so physically the ALEE should be $-I_{\text{Li}}$ and $-I_H$ in the HOMO-dominated regions of the Li and H atoms, respectively. Around the H atom,

FIG. 2: The Kohn-Sham ALEE of Eq. (19) and wavefunction ALEE of Eq. (20) obtained from the FCI/u-pc-2 wavefunction for a stretched LiH molecule. I_{Li} and I_H are the EKT ionization energies from Table I.

FIG. 3: The wavefunction ALEE computed by Eq. (20) from the FCI/u-pc-2 wavefunction of LiH for various internuclear distances.

FIG. 4: The wavefunction ALEE computed by Eq. (20) from the HF/u-pc-2 wavefunction of LiH for various internuclear distances.

the difference between $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ attains a constant value of $(I_{\text{H}} - I_{\text{Li}})$, which is precisely the height of the step exhibited by $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$. Thus, the localized upshift of the exact $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ in a stretched diatomic is due to the step behavior of the quantity $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ which assumes values equal to the negative ionization energies of the constituent atoms in the HOMO-dominated regions of these atoms. A parallel theoretical explanation of the step in terms of quantities $v^{N-1}(\mathbf{r})$ and $v_s^{N-1}(\mathbf{r})$ may be found in Ref. 10.

The step structure of $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ is not developed at short internuclear distances when the two atoms strongly overlap, but becomes more and more pronounced with increasing bond length, tending to a well-defined step when the atoms are completely separated (Fig. 3).

The step structure of $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ is a manifestation of long-range correlation effects, so it would be absent in the Hartree-Fock (HF) theory. This is illustrated with plots

FIG. 5: The response potential constructed by Eq. (18) from the FCI/u-pc-2 wavefunction of LiH for various internuclear distances.

TABLE II: Atomic charges in LiH for various internuclear distances (R) obtained from the exchange-correlation potentials generated by the RKS method using the FCI and HF wavefunctions in the u-pc-2 basis set. BLYP and B3LYP charges computed with the same basis set are included for comparison. All calculations are spin-restricted.

R/R_e	Atomic charges $q_{\text{Li}} = -q_{\text{H}}$, a.u.			
	FCI ^a	HF ^a	BLYP	B3LYP
1.0	0.754	0.782	0.722	0.741
1.5	0.620	0.710	0.591	0.629
2.0	0.388	0.695	0.496	0.550
2.5	0.109	0.677	0.422	0.479
3.0	0.020	0.646	0.373	0.426
3.5	0.005	0.613	0.343	0.390
∞	0.000	0.432	0.234	0.263

^aDirect calculations from wavefunction-based densities give nearly the same values.

of $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ obtained from the HF/u-pc-2 wavefunctions of LiH (Fig. 4). Similar to the Kohn-Sham ALEE, the HF ALEE exhibits no steps at any internuclear distance.

Finally, Fig. 5 shows the entire response term as a function of internuclear distance in the dissociating LiH molecule. Observe that the response potentials in Fig. 5 do not have any wiggles or dips commonly seen when the Kohn-Sham potentials are fitted to Gaussian-basis electron densities.²⁴ This is because our expression for $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ is a difference of two well-behaved terms given by Eqs. (19) and (20), neither of which oscillates or diverges even when the orbitals $\phi_i(\mathbf{x})$ and $f_j(\mathbf{x})$ are represented in terms of Gaussian basis functions.

It is also instructive to verify that the atomic charges on Li and H in a separated LiH are actually zero when the density of the system is generated by a Kohn-Sham potential with a proper step structure. To this end,

FIG. 6: The wavefunction ALEE computed by Eq. (20) from the (8,8)CASSCF/6-31* wavefunction of NaCl at R_e and $3R_e$. Note the logarithmic scale on the vertical axis.

we computed $\rho^{\text{KS}}(\mathbf{r})$ corresponding to various exchange-correlation potentials of dissociating LiH and then extracted the atomic charges on Li and H by fitting them to reproduce the dipole moment of the molecule. Calculations using the exchange-correlation potentials generated from FCI/u-pc-2 wavefunctions correctly predict that the atomic charges on Li and H tend to zero with increasing bond length (Table II). This is to be contrasted with large spurious charges obtained from the exchange-correlation potentials corresponding to the HF/u-pc-2 wavefunction or from standard density-functional approximations.

Although we focused on a small molecule (LiH) described at the FCI level, similar results are obtained for any heteronuclear diatomic using any approximate wavefunction that includes static correlation effects. Consider, for instance, $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ computed for the NaCl molecule from the 8-electron, 8-orbital complete active space self-consistent field (CASSCF) wavefunction in the 6-31G* basis set (Fig. 6). Even at this modest level of theory, the correlated-wavefunction ALEE has a fully de-

veloped step structure at $3R_e$ ($R_e = 2.3609 \text{ \AA}$), complete with tell-tale step between the Na and Cl atoms.

We have also observed that it is particularly easy to see the step structure of $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$ for a stretched molecule when the correlated wavefunction is computed in a very compact basis set such as STO-3G. This is because the HOMO-dominated region of the more electronegative atom described with a compact basis set is more localized and has better-defined boundaries than when the same atom is described with a high-quality basis.

IV. CONCLUSION

The exact exchange-correlation potential of a dissociating heteronuclear diatomic molecule AB builds up a counterionic field that prevents the formation of spurious fractional charges on the separated atoms. Gritsenko and Baerends¹⁰ traced the origin of this field to the response term of $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ by showing that the two components of $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ assume different constant values (related to the ionization energies of the isolated atoms) in the HOMO-dominated regions of the atoms in a stretched molecule. In this work, we illustrated this mechanism in detail by computing the two components of $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$ and displaying their behavior as functions of internuclear distance. Our analysis most directly demonstrates that the step structure of $v_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r})$ is linked to the step-like drop of $\bar{\epsilon}^{\text{WF}}(\mathbf{r})$, the wavefunction component of $v_{\text{resp}}(\mathbf{r})$, in the HOMO-dominated region of the more electronegative atom.

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